

ICCM22

MELBOURNE AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Water Vapor Corrosion Behavior and Failure Mechanism of Plasma Sprayed Mullite/Lu₂Si₂O₇-Lu₂SiO₅ Coatings

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Research Background and Experimental Methodology

Abstract:

A new coating with mullite as the inner layer and Lu₂Si₂O₇-Lu₂SiO₅ (lutetium disilicate-lutetium monosilicate, LuDS-LuMS) composite as the top layer was designed and fabricated on the surface of porous SiC substrate by atmospheric plasma spraying (APS). The microstructure evolution, phase transformation, inter-diffusion and failure mechanism of the coated samples during steam cycling at 1450 °C were systematically investigated. The results indicated that the coated samples maintain weight gain and the average weight gain rate is 1.12×10⁻¹ mg/cm² h. The thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) mismatches between the coating and the substrate as well as between the two ceramic layers have produced a thermal mismatch stress. In addition, the chemical reaction induced the sintering of LuDS-LuMS layer, the amorphous-crystalline phase transformation and the transformation between LuDS and LuMS phases could result in aging stress. With the accumulation of thermal mismatch stress and aging stress, the through and horizontal cracks have appeared in the coating, leading to the coating failure.

Background :

- In 1997, Opila et al demonstrated that Si-based composites were vulnerable to recession by water vapor at elevated temperature (i.e. oxidation and hydroxide formation. See Eqs. at right)¹
- A protective layer, composed of rare earth silicates (RES), was proposed to protect against recession.²
- It was found that lutetium silicate composite tended to have better protection against recession over di-silicates (i.e. RE₂Si₂O₇) which led to their use in the current study.³

Recession at high temperature due to water vapor²

experimental methodology and experimental setup:

- 1450°C 95% H₂O-5% air
- The flow velocity of water vapor was 0.54 m/s
- For each thermal cycling
- corrosion test, the samples were firstly heated for 2.5 h at 1450 °C, cooled down to the room temperature within 2 min by compressed air jet.
- Analyses are made with X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to understand how the surface changes after exposure
- An electronic balance with a sensitivity of ± 0.1 mg was used to quantify the weight change of the coated samples before and after thermal cycling corrosion test

X-ray diffraction

- XRD patterns for the feedstock powders of mullite and LuDS-LuMS and the corresponding as-sprayed coatings by APS.

- The Rietveld refinement of experimental XRD data of mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating surface after exposure to water vapor at 1450 °C for different hours. (a) 0 h; (b) 100 h; (c) 150 h.

Microstructure evolution and mass change

- Macrographs of SiC substrate coated with mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating (a) before and (b) after 150 h corrosion

- Variation in weight gain with the steam cycling cycles and steam cycling time.

- SEM microstructures on (a-b) the surface and (b-d) the cross-section of the as-sprayed (a,c) mullite and (b,d) mullite/LuDS-LuMS coatings deposited on SiC substrate.

- Microstructure and (d) EDS-line analysis on the cross-section of porous SiC with mullite/LuDS-LuMS coating after 150 h water vapor corrosion test, and (b-c) high magnification SEM images of region (A) and (B) marked in Figure (a), respectively.

Summary

Conclusions:

- New bi-layer mullite/LuDS-LuMS EBCs have been successfully fabricated on the SiC substrate by APS
- The coating, with a good interfacial bonding and corrosion resistance, can endure 150 h steam cycling test (60 cycles) at 1450 °C
- The coating maintain weight gain and average weight gain rate is 1.12×10⁻¹ mg/cm² h
- The appearance of through and horizontal cracks are attributed to the accumulation of thermal mismatch stress and aging stress.

The CTE mismatch between the coating and the substrate as well as between the two ceramic layers produces thermal mismatch stress. The chemical reaction induce the sintering of LuDS-LuMS layer, the amorphous-crystalline phase transformation and the transformation between LuDS and LuMS result in the aging stress. With the accumulation of thermal mismatch stress and aging stress, the through and horizontal cracks have appeared in the coating, leading to the coating failure.

References:

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